

MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF FIBROUS CAPSULE WHEN USING ANTISEPTIC EFFECT WITH LASER

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Summary: The article presents the results of experimental and morphological studies aimed at solving the issue of treating the cavity of an echinococcal cyst with various antiseptics, and assessing the effectiveness of laser radiation. The experiments were carried out in the laboratory of the state institution “Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center named after Academician V.Vakhidov”. The main objective of the experimental study was to evaluate the effect of laser exposure in combination with treatment with various antiseptics on the germinal elements of echinococcal fluid and the fibrous layer of the capsule of parasitic cysts. For this purpose, the study is divided into 2 large series. Each series was carried out sequentially. In the first series, the authors gave a macroscopic (visual) and microscopic assessment of each sample

Key words: experiment, macroscopy, echinococcus, fibrous capsule, processing, laser irradiation, microscopy.

Relevance. Many studies have found that germinal elements occur in the fibrous layer of the capsule. This, in turn, leads to relapses of echinococcosis [1,2,5,7]. For this purpose, at present, during surgery for liver echinococcosis, it is recommended to treat the residual cavity with various chemical antiseptics (formalin solution, iodine, alcohol, hydrogen peroxide, etc.) and physical factors (ultrasound, laser radiation, thermal exposure, etc.) [3,4 ,6,8].

Aim. Our goal was to study the effect of antiseptics on the fibrous capsule of the cyst cavity in a model of liver echinococcosis, treating their cavities with various antiseptics and conducting a morphological comparative study.

Methodology. Male rats of 2-3 months of age weighing 200-220 g were selected. The animals were not fed 1 day before the experiment. Only sufficient water is given. On the day of the experiment, light sleep is induced under

inhalation anesthesia (isoflurane). They are then immobilized in a position with the abdominal wall elevated in the surgical field, which allows the rats to specifically immobilize their movements. After the upper laparotomy, the abdominal area of the rat (an imaginary line 1-2 cm drawn down from the wedge-shaped part of the sternum) is cleared of hair, treated with a 70% alcohol solution, and a laparotomy 1.5-2 cm long is performed. After opening the peritoneum into the liver 3-5 pre-prepared echinococcal vesicles with an average diameter of 0.5 cm are implanted. Then the wound is closed with sutures. The wound is treated with a 10% betadine solution. After surgery, the rats were given sufficient fluid and food in the first half of the day. The formation of echinococcal cysts in the liver of experimental animals was completed 1 month after surgery.

Research series:

We divided the experimental animals into 4 groups:

Group 1 – control. In this case, the cyst cavity of experimental animals was treated with an 80% glycerol solution.

In group 2, the cyst cavity was treated with a 3% alcohol solution of iodine.

In the 3rd group, after treating the cyst cavity with the antiseptic solution FarGALS, the fibrous cavity of the cyst was irradiated for 1 minute using LILI in the green spectrum.

In group 4, the cyst cavity was treated with a 96% ethanol solution.

There were at least 4-5 animals in each group.

In the experimental model, after treatment of the cyst cavity in experimental animals, the wound was sutured and biomaterials obtained from liver echinococcosis cysts were assessed morphologically on days 1, 3 and 5.

In this series, mainly after treating the cyst with various antiseptics, the state of the scolex on the surface of the fibrous layer and changes in the architecture of the fibrous layer, parafibrosis (between healthy liver tissue and fibrous tissue) were determined as the main criteria and compared with the observed morphological changes.

Microscopy results:

Microscopic assessment of biomaterials obtained after the 1st day of the experiment showed that the effect of the FarGALS antiseptic liquid on the scolex was observed already on the 1st day of the experiment, with morphological changes in the form of swelling of the protoscolex shell in cracks of different sizes on the surface and in the fibrous capsule, mainly with a violation of the

integrity of the scolex wall and the release of intracellular inclusions into the surrounding tissues. These changes indicate complete disintegration of the scolex.

Under the influence of the antiseptic liquid FarGALS and LILI, from the first day of the study, predominantly exudative-proliferative processes of inflammation in the architecture of the fibrous layer, congestion of blood vessels in the parafibrous layer, diapedesis of the periphery of blood vessels were clearly revealed, and in groups with other types of antiseptics in the cavity of the fibrous membrane, alterative neurobiotics predominated. dystrophic changes. In this case, leukocyte-eosinophilic infiltrates and signs of edema in the parafibrous layer predominated. Hyperchromia and edema were observed in the hepatocytes of this area.

By the 3rd day of the experiment, in the group exposed to the antiseptic liquid FarGALS and LILI, the above processes occurred predominantly with a predominance of proliferative-regenerative properties. In this case, the gaps between the fibrous layers are reduced. This is mainly due to the formation of connective tissue as a result of the proliferation of fibroblasts in this area. Infiltration in parafibrous areas is practically absent. In some areas, focal or diffuse lymphocytic-histocytic infiltration is noted. Edema disappeared in hepatocytes in the parafibrous zone. Such changes are especially noticeable on day 5 of the experiment. Thin fibrous connective tissue fibers form in the fibrous layer. During this period, the regenerative-compensatory stage of inflammation began to predominate.

In groups with other types of antiseptics, several protoscolexes were observed among the fibrous layer of the hydatid cyst model. At this time, the exudative inflammatory process of inflammation predominates. Lymphocytic infiltrates are predominantly observed in the parafibrous zone. Edema-dystrophic changes are observed in the hepatocytes bordering this area.

Only on the 5th day of the experiment does the inflammatory exudative-proliferative process begin to predominate. Scolexes with eccentric inclusions and parafibrous swellings between the fibrous layers are preserved. Lymphocytic-histocytic infiltration begins to join this process. As a result, the formation of rough fibrous tissue increases.

Conclusions Also, another important conclusion is that not a single traditionally used antiseptic (alcohol, iodine, glycerin) provides a complete germicidal effect on the germinal elements of echinococcus, localized in the thickness of the fibrous capsule. The use of the antiseptic FarGALS, which has photosensitizing

properties under the influence of LILI in the green spectrum, has an active effect on them (mainly due to active hydrogen) due to the appearance of radicals, which in turn causes oxidation of the protoscolex membrane, resulting in a parasitocidal effect. This directly causes the complete destruction of the scolex, especially in cases where there is a possibility of their preservation in the thickness of the fibrous layer, which accordingly prevents the likelihood of local relapse of liver echinococcosis.

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